

Analytical investigation on the structural performance of RC column with 3D-printed concrete permanent formwork

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Abstract. Mechanical anisotropy of 3D printed concrete (3DPC) has been often considered harmful; however, its detrimental effect is not so serious or even negligible in some applications, such as permanent formwork made of 3DPC. Recently, several previous studies have demonstrated that 3DPC permanent formwork for reinforced concrete (RC) column construction can enhance the structural performance due to its higher confinement effects. However, no comprehensive research has yet been conducted on the effects of influential factors, including material properties, interlayer bonding properties, dimensions of 3DPC, bonding properties between 3DPC and inner core RC, and loading conditions. This research aims to evaluate the effects of various factors on the structural performance of RC columns with 3DPC permanent formwork by using finite element method (FEM)-based nonlinear structural analysis. Specifically, the behaviors of 3DPC-RC columns under either uniaxial compression or reversed cyclic loading, which were reported in previous experimental studies, were investigated. Properly considering the material properties, structural dimensions, boundary, and loading conditions of the columns, the FEM analysis could reproduce the force-displacement curves observed in the experiment. The enhanced load-bearing capacity due to confinement effects could also be reproduced. The simulated failure modes also agreed with those in the experiment. Subsequently, a parametric study using the FEM analysis was conducted varying bonding properties of 3DPC. The analysis results indicated that the interlayer bonding properties have relatively small effects on the load-bearing capacity of the 3DPC-RC composite column.

Keywords: 3D Printing, Permanent Formwork, Mechanical Anisotropy, Structural Analysis, Uniaxial Compression, Reversed Cyclic Loading.

1 Introduction

Mechanical anisotropy of 3D Printed Concrete (3DPC) is frequently considered a deleterious characteristic; it introduces large variability in its mechanical properties depending on the direction of the applied stresses relative to the orientation of the printed layers. The layer-by-layer printing process can create weak interfacial bonds between the printed filaments, which often results in lower strength and stiffness in the direction perpendicular to the printing layers compared to the direction parallel to the layers [1]. Previous studies investigated mechanical properties of 3DPC specimens that were collected from relatively large printed objects (e.g., [2], [3], [4]). They found that mechanical properties such as

compressive and flexural strengths of the 3D printed specimens were significantly affected by their loading and printing directions. Thus, the mechanical anisotropy of 3DPC seems to be a significant technical challenge, especially in its structural applications. The magnitude of the mechanical property degradation, however, depends on the combination of loading and printing directions; thus, in some applications, its effect might be almost negligible.

Recently, Zhu et al. studied the structural performance of reinforced concrete (RC) columns with 3DPC permanent formwork under uniaxial compression [5]. Their experimental results indicated that the load-bearing capacity and stiffness of the 3DPC-RC composite columns were higher than those of the counterpart cast-in-place columns using conventional formwork. Meanwhile, Kinomura et al. investigated the structural performance of a 3DPC-RC composite column under reversed cyclic loading [6]. They found that the outer 3DPC shell and the inner RC core behaved as a single unit, and that the load-bearing capacity and the energy absorption capability were significantly enhanced compared to the regular RC column. Both studies attributed the enhanced structural performance to the confinement effects of the 3DPC permanent formwork.

As the preceding studies have demonstrated, 3DPC permanent formwork for RC column construction appears to be a promising application that can enhance the overall structural performance while offering many other benefits such as the higher geometrical freedom in design, shorter construction time, reduced cost, and less material waste [7, 8]. However, the role of the interlayer bonding properties in this application has not yet been fully discussed. In addition, effects of various factors, including material properties and dimensions of 3DPC and interfacial bonding properties between the outer 3DPC shell and the inner RC core, remain unclear.

The present research aims to evaluate the effects of various factors on the structural performance of 3DPC-RC composite columns by using finite element method (FEM)-based nonlinear structural analysis. Specifically, the two preceding studies mentioned above (3DPC-RC columns under either uniaxial compression [5] or reversed cyclic loading [6]) are investigated. First, the analysis method is validated by comparing the reported experimental data and simulation results in each case. Then, sensitivity analysis is conducted to evaluate the effects of various factors.

2 Analysis Method

In this study, COM3 – a FEM-based structural analysis program developed by Maekawa et al. [9] – was used. This program incorporates a smeared crack approach with constitutive laws of 3-dimensional RC elements that can consider multi-directional, non-orthogonal cracking. The models and the program have been validated and verified with various experimental data of RC structures under static, dynamic, and fatigue loading [9, 10, 11].

Figure 1 shows the schematic illustrations of the constitutive laws used in this study. The nonlinear path-dependent constitutive models for compression, tension, and shear were used for finite elements representing the inner RC core and the outer 3DPC shell, with appropriate model parameters for each material. Particularly, a tension-softening parameter, c , should be set according to the post-cracking behavior in tension for each material. The value of c for normal RC elements was set at 0.4 to consider the tension stiffening by rebars according to the past research [9]. The brittle behavior of plain concrete can be represented by a larger value of c , which is calculated based on the fracture energy and reference length of the finite element. A smaller c value leads to higher toughness (i.e., lower stress reduction after the peak), which can reflect the tension-softening behavior of fiber reinforced concrete. For the interlayer between adjacent 3DPC filaments and for the interface between the 3DPC shell and the inner RC, 2-dimensional interface elements using the shear transfer model [9] with modified model parameters were employed. The shear transfer model was originally developed to represent the aggregate interlock along cracked planes in concrete. It is primarily governed by the bonding strength, tensile opening stiffness, shear stiffness, and the maximum aggregate size of these planes. The mechanical behaviors of the interlayer and interface regions in the present study are supposed to be reproduced if model parameters reflecting the surface roughness of crack planes are appropriately set. In essence, the tension model

represents the brittle behavior for the stress normal to the plane, and the shear model incorporates the effect of the confining stress (i.e., compressive stress normal to the plane) on the shear stress parallel to the plane. The details of the models can be found elsewhere [9].

Fig. 1. Schematic illustrations of the constitutive models used in this study [9]: (a) compression, tension, and shear models used for the inner RC and the outer 3DPC shell, (b) shear transfer model used for the interlayer between the 3DPC filaments and the interface between the outer 3DPC and the inner RC.

3 Validation and Verification of Numerical Analysis

3.1 Case I: Uniaxial Compression

Overview of Preceding Experimental Study by Zhu et al. 2021. Zhu et al. experimentally studied the structural performance of 3DPC-RC composite columns under uniaxial compression, focusing on the influence of the steel reinforcement ratio of the inner RC core [5]. Figure 2 illustrates the design of the 6 column specimens. Three cases, (a), (b), and (c), used conventional formwork and the other three, (d), (e), and (f), incorporated the 3DPC formwork. Each specimen was designated according to the number of longitudinal steel rebars. The diameter and height were 250 mm and 500 mm, respectively, in all cases. The thickness of the 3DPC formwork was 25mm.

Fig. 2. Cross sections and reinforcement details of column specimens tested by Zhu et al.: (a) cast plain concrete, (b) cast RC with 6 longitudinal rebars, (c) cast RC with 8 longitudinal rebars, (d) cast plain concrete with 3DPC formwork, (e) cast 6-rebar RC with 3DPC formwork, (f) cast 8-rebar RC with 3DPC formwork (based on [5]).

The 28-day compressive strength of conventional concrete used for the inner core was 30 MPa. Details of the ingredients and mix proportions were not reported in [5]. The 3DPC was a cement-based mortar with a compressive strength of 40 MPa. Short polyethylene fibers and calcium carbonate whiskers were employed as the reinforcement materials to mitigate the effect of shrinkage of the 3DPC. Each column specimen was tested under uniaxial compression using a hydraulic testing machine.

Analysis Configurations. Figure 3 shows the FE model used in the analysis. The column dimensions are identical to those in the experiment. The mesh size for the vertical direction is the same as the printed filament thickness (10 mm). The reinforcement ratios in the RC elements were set to represent the actual reinforcement details. Perfectly elastic solid elements with a stiffness of 210 GPa were added at the top and bottom of the column to represent the steel bearing plates of the loading machine.

For the interlayers (i.e., between adjacent printed filaments) and the interfaces (i.e., between the inner cast core and the outer printed shell), perfect bonding was assumed in the analysis for the model validation, according to the report in [5]. In the sensitivity analysis to investigate the effects of the interlayers/interfaces, 2-dimensional interface elements with appropriate model parameters were used to represent the behaviors of weak bonding.

The input material properties are listed in Table 1. The compressive strengths of cast concrete and of the printed mortar are the same as the reported values, from which the tensile strength and elastic modulus of concrete were estimated according to JSCE Standards [12]. Since detailed information of the rebars was not reported in [5], mechanical properties of commonly used steel rebars were employed as the simulation input. A loading rate of 0.2 mm/min was used in the analysis, as in the experiment.

Fig. 3. FE model used in the analysis for the uniaxial compression case.

Table 1. Input material properties of the analysis for the uniaxial compression case.

Materials	Compressive strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)
Inner cast concrete	30	2.25	–	28
Outer printed mortar	40	3.0	–	31
Steel rebar	–	600	400	210

Results and Discussion. Figure 4 shows the measured and simulated load-displacement curves of the 6 cases. The analysis results appear to match the overall trends observed in the experiment. First, the load-bearing capacity in each case was well reproduced in the analysis. In addition, the increase in the load-bearing capacity and stiffness of the composite columns compared with the corresponding cast-in-place columns can be seen in both the experiment and the analysis.

Fig. 4. Load-displacement curves of the experiment (data from [5]) and the analysis.

Zhu et al. attributed the enhanced structural performance of the composite columns to the relatively higher compressive strength of the printed shell and to the resultant higher confinement effect [5]. The analysis results in the present study also indicated the higher confinement effect. Figure 5 shows the simulated maximum principal strain map at failure on the outer surface of each column. The range of the color contour is the same in all cases. The strain levels around the middle of the composite columns are significantly lower than those of the corresponding cast-in-place columns, implying the bulging deformation and concrete cover spalling are suppressed due to the 3DPC shell.

Fig. 5. Simulated maximum principal strain map of each case at failure.

3.2 Case II: Reversed Cyclic Loading

Overview of Preceding Experimental Study by Kinomura et al. 2023. Kinomura et al. studied the structural performance of a 3DPC-RC composite column under reversed cyclic loading [6]. Figure 6 shows the design drawing of the 3DPC-RC-column. While the cross-sectional dimensions gradually change along the height direction near the top of the column, the diameter is 530 mm from the bottom of the column to a height of 600 mm. The thickness of the 3DPC formwork is 50 mm from the bottom to the top of the column. However, in the fabrication of the 3DPC formwork, they found that the actual column diameter near the footing was 543 mm due to the deformation of printed mortar filaments caused by their self-weight. Thus, they prepared a regular RC column with a diameter of 543 mm as a control specimen, using conventional formwork. The control specimen is a regular column without any change in cross-sectional dimensions along the height direction.

Fig. 6. Design drawing of the 3DPC-RC column tested by Kinomura et al. (based on [6]).

For the reversed cyclic loading test on each case, a vertical compression force of 50 kN was first applied on the top of the loading stub. Then, the reversed cyclic loading was applied by the horizontal jacks attached to both sides of the stub at a height of 1500 mm from the top of the footing. At the beginning of the test, the applied horizontal displacement was increased by 5 mm for every cycle. The increment, 5 mm, was determined based on the horizontal displacement at which the axial rebar placed at the tensile outer edge of the control column specimen yielded. Then, after reaching the total displacement of 70 mm, the displacement increment for every cycle was increased to 10 mm. The control column specimen failed at 100 mm. For the 3DPC-RC composite column, loading continued with an increment of 20 mm per cycle. After reaching the total displacement of 160 mm, the composite column was pushed over up to 230 mm in the positive direction.

Analysis Configurations. Figure 7 shows the FE model used in the analysis. The column dimensions and steel reinforcement configurations were determined based on the experiment. For the interfaces (i.e., between the outer 3DPC shell and the inner RC core), perfect bonding was assumed in the analysis for the model validation, according to the report in [6]. On the other hand, 2-dimensional interface elements were used for the interlayers (i.e., between adjacent printed filaments) because significant mechanical anisotropy in its tensile strength was reported in [6]. Interface elements were also inserted between the column and the footing to reflect the damage on the column-footing joint found in the experiment.

Fig. 7. FE model used in the analysis for the reversed cyclic loading case.

Table 2 lists the input mechanical properties of the cast concrete, 3DPC, and steel rebars, which were determined and estimated according to [6]. On the other hand, the bonding strength of the interface elements was assumed to be 2.77 MPa. This assumption is based on splitting tensile tests performed orthogonally on the interface between two adjacent printed layers as reported in [6]. The assumed tensile opening stiffness and shear stiffness of the interlayers were calculated according to the compressive strength of the printed material using JSCE standard equations [12]. The values used for the tensile opening stiffness and shear stiffness are 3.36 GPa and 1.4 GPa, respectively. The maximum aggregate size, representing the interface roughness, was assumed to be 1mm to reflect the smooth surface between adjacent printed layers after cracking. The loading condition in the analysis was identical to that in the experiment.

Table 2. Input material properties of the analysis for the reversed cyclic loading case.

Series	Materials	Compressive strength (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)
Control RC column	Cast concrete	38	3.3	–	30
	Axial rebar	–	588	392	206
	Hoop rebar	–	588	374	206
3DPC-RC composite column	Inner cast concrete	41	3.5	–	30
	Outer printed mortar	52	4.5	–	33
	Axial rebar	–	785	386	206
	Hoop rebar	–	785	346	206

Results and Discussion. Figure 8 shows the loading hysteresis loops of the control and composite specimens. The analysis results appear to well reproduce the overall trends in the experimental results. In the case of the control column specimen, the maximum horizontal forces are 124 kN and 121 kN in the experiment and the analysis, respectively, while those are 142 kN and 149 kN in the case of the 3DPC-RC composite column.

Fig. 8. Load-displacement curves of the experiment (data from [6]) and the analysis.

Figure 9 shows the observed failure patterns and simulated principal strain maps of both cases. In the control case, the observed concrete spalling around the bottom of the column could be reflected in the corresponding high strained regions in the analysis. In the case of the 3DPC-RC composite column, the simulation result indicated a failure at the interface elements for the column-footing joint, which agrees with the finding in the experiment.

Fig. 9. Observed failure patterns and simulated maximum principal strain maps at failure.

The results and discussion in this section have confirmed that the constitutive models and the analysis program used in this study are valid for the investigated cases. Then, sensitivity analysis using the validated program was conducted, which is detailed in the following section.

4 Sensitivity analysis with respect to bonding strength

The sensitivity analysis was conducted for the uniaxial compression case discussed in Section 3.1. Based on the Case (d) 3DPC-0 as a reference, two additional cases were examined: Case (d-1) where weak interlayer bonding (i.e., between adjacent printed mortar filaments) was assumed and Case (d-2) where weak interfacial bonding (i.e., between the inner RC core and the outer 3DPC shell) was assumed. In Case (d-1), two-dimensional interface elements were inserted in the interlayer regions. The bonding strength of the interlayers was assumed to be 1.5 MPa, i.e., half of the tensile strength of the printed mortar. The assumed tensile opening stiffness and shear stiffness of the interlayers were calculated based on the compressive strength of the printed material using the standard equations of JSCE [12]. The values used for the tensile opening stiffness and shear stiffness are 3.16 GPa and 1.32 GPa, respectively. The maximum aggregate size, representing the interface roughness, was assumed to be 1mm to reflect the smooth surface between the adjacent printed layers after cracking. The other analysis configurations of Case (d-1) were identical to those used in the Case (d). On the other hand, for case (d-2), the bonding strength was assumed to be 1.125 MPa, i.e., half of the tensile strength of the cast concrete. The used tensile opening stiffness and shear stiffness are 2.86 GPa and 1.19 GPa, respectively. The maximum aggregate size was assumed to be 10mm to reflect the rough surface between the cast concrete and the printed formwork after cracking. The other analysis configurations of case (d-2) were identical to those used in the Case (d).

Figure 10 shows the simulated load-displacement curve and maximum principal strain map on the vertical cross section of each case. When comparing the original Case (d) and Case (d-1), a slight decrease in the load bearing capacity can be seen, but the difference is less than 4%. Thus, the weak bonding and the resultant mechanical anisotropy of 3DPC appear to have limited effects on the structural performance of the composite column under uniaxial compression. This agrees with a finding in previous studies [e.g., 13] that the mechanical anisotropy of 3DPC is insignificant when the loading direction is perpendicular to the weak interlayer planes. It should be noted, however, that the ductility (i.e., deformation at failure) is 15% lower than the original Case (d). Indeed, a local failure occurred at the weak interlayers in the analysis, as indicated in the principal strain map in Fig. 10.

In Case (d-2), the load-bearing capacity is 6% smaller than the original Case (d), and the ductility is 15% lower. This trend is similar to that observed in Case (d-1). However, unlike Case (d-1), a sudden load drop after the peak can be seen in Case (d-2), indicating a brittle failure of the column. This behavior might be attributed to separation between the inner RC core and the outer 3DPC shell. The maximum principal strain map at failure shown in Fig. 10 indicates a relatively large bulge of the column and separated elements between the inner and outer parts near the top and the bottom of the column.

Fig. 10. Simulated load-displacement curve and principal strain map on the vertical cross section of each case.

5 Conclusions

This study has demonstrated by numerical analysis that 3DPC permanent formwork for RC column construction is a promising application. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- FEM-based structural analysis using 3-dimensional solid elements and 2-dimensional interface elements with suitable constitutive laws can reproduce the overall structural behavior of 3DPC-RC composite columns under either uniaxial compression or reversed cyclic loading.
- The analysis results suggest that the load bearing capacity and ductility of 3DPC-RC composite columns are enhanced due to the confinement effect of the 3DPC formwork, which agrees with the finding in preceding studies.
- Weak interlayer bonding between printed mortar filaments has limited effects on the overall structural performance of 3DPC-RC composite columns.
- Weak interfacial bonding between the outer 3DPC shell and the inner RC core also has insignificant effects on the load-bearing capacity of the composite column, but a brittle failure might happen after the peak load because of the separation between the inner and outer parts.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Council for Science, Technology and Innovation (CSTI), Cross-ministerial Strategic Innovation Promotion Program (SIP), the 3rd period of SIP “Smart Infrastructure Management System” Grant Number JPJ012187 (Funding agency: Public Works Research Institute) and JSPS KAKENHI Grant Number JP21H01403.

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